

Spin physics lecture

PHENIX school
June 21st
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Interaction	Energy scale	System size	Main topics	(quasi) participants
Electro-magnetic	eV-keV	$>10^{-10}$ m	Atoms, molecules, condensed matter	Nuclei + chg. leptons
QCD (effective theories)	MeV	$<10^{-14}$ m	Nuclear structure	Protons, neutrons
QCD (non-perturbative)	~ 1 GeV	10^{-15} m	Parton distribution and fragmentation functions	Quarks, Gluons
QCD (perturbative)	>1 GeV	$<10^{-15}$ m	Partonic hard scattering	Quarks, Gluons
Electroweak	~ 100 GeV	10^{-18} m	Higgs, parity violation, sea quark access	Quarks, leptons, W,Z (+Higgs) Bosons
Gravity	10^{19} GeV	10^{-32} m	Extra dimensions, black holes...	Strings, any massive particle

- Nearly all the mass of the visible universe from proton/neutron masses
- Proton: |**up,up,down**> valence quarks, sea quarks, gluons
- Nucleon mass ($1\text{Gev}/c^2$) not from Higgs mechanism (only 2-3 MeV/ c^2 from Higgs), but from **quantum chromo(color) dynamics, QCD**

Spin Structure of the Nucleon

$$\frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2}\Delta\Sigma + \Delta G + \mathcal{L}_G + \mathcal{L}_q$$

$$\Delta\Sigma = \int dx [(\Delta u(x) + \Delta\bar{u}(x)) + (\Delta d(x) + \Delta\bar{d}(x)) + (\Delta s(x) + \Delta\bar{s}(x))]$$

- Helicity structure: total longitudinal spin, decomposed in quark spins ($\Delta\Sigma$), gluon spin, and orbital angular momenta

- Transverse spin and transverse momentum dependence: Transverse spin contribution, spin-orbit correlations, 3D momentum picture

Strength of the QCD interaction

Electromagnetic interaction

- Electric charge e
- Mediator: Photons
- Coupling strength : $1/137$

Strong interaction (QCD)

- Color charge (quarks and gluons)
- Mediator: Gluons
- Coupling strength: depends on the energy

- Asymptotic freedom (high scale): perturbative treatment, calculable
- Color confinement (low scale): only color-neutral (white) objects allowed

Confinement and fragmentation

- **Confined objects :**
 - Cannot be extracted from perturbative calculations
 - Parton distribution functions (quark, gluon distribution in nucleon/nucleii): DIS, hadron collisions, Lattice simulations
 - Fragmentation functions (formation of hadrons from high-energetic partons) : e^+e^- , SIDIS, p+p

Gluonic String breaks down into $q\bar{q}$ pairs

DIS Kinematics

$$\frac{d^2\sigma}{dx dQ^2} \stackrel{LO}{\propto} \sum_{q, \bar{q}} e_q^2 q(x, Q^2)$$

Quark distribution functions:
(anti)quark q in nucleon with
momentum fraction x

$Q^2 = -q^2$ $= -(k - k')^2$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Squared Momentum transfer of photon/Z <i>(Resolution)</i>
$x_B = \frac{Q^2}{2Pq}$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bjorken scaling variable x, at high Q^2 momentum fraction of quark ($0 < x < 1$)
$k^+ = xP^+$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inelasticity y (sometimes called depolarization factor, $0 < y < 1$)
$y = \frac{qP}{kP}$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inelasticity y (sometimes called depolarization factor, $0 < y < 1$)
$W^2 = (P + q)^2$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mass of hadronic final state W^2 (typically above 4 to avoid resonances)

• Hard scales: $Q^2 \gg 1 \text{ GeV}^2$ otherwise photo-production

• Relation with CMS energy $Q^2 = s x y$

DIS cross section

- Cross section:

$$\frac{d\sigma^2}{dxdy} = \frac{2\pi\alpha^2}{Q^4} L^{\mu\nu} W_{\mu\nu}$$

- Leptonic Tensor straightforward (EM/EW calculation)
- Hadronic tensor related via optical theorem to *Im* part of forward scattering amplitude:

$$W_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int d^4z e^{iqz} \langle P, S | J_\mu(z) J_\nu | P, S \rangle$$

Unpolarized proton structure

$$\frac{d^2\sigma^i}{dx dy} = \frac{2\pi\alpha^2}{xyQ^2} \eta^i [Y_+ F_2^i - y^2 F_L^i]$$

$$F_L^i = F_2^i - 2xF_1^i$$

$$Y_{\pm} = 1 \pm (1-y)^2$$

$$F_2^\gamma = x \sum_q e_q^2 (q + \bar{q})$$

Neutral current

- F_2 (and F_1) measure the sum of quark and antiquark distribution in the nucleon or nuclei
- The majority of our knowledge on the unpolarized PDFs is coming from F_2 measurements

Unpolarized proton structure, EW included

$$\frac{d^2\sigma^i}{dxdy} = \frac{2\pi\alpha^2}{xyQ^2} \eta^i [Y_+ F_2^i \pm Y_- x F_3^i - y^2 F_L^i]$$

$$F_L^i = F_2^i - 2xF_1^i$$

$$Y_{\pm} = 1 \pm (1-y)^2$$

- F_L measures the violation of the Callen-Gross relation \rightarrow glue
- Flavor information from γZ interference, Z exchange and in particular charged current (W exchange) interactions
- Z and W parts of F_3 depend on lepton helicity

$$F_2^\gamma = x \sum_q e_q^2 (q + \bar{q})$$

$$F_2^{\gamma Z} = x \sum_q 2e_q g_V^q (q + \bar{q})$$

$$F_2^Z = x \sum_q (g_V^q{}^2 + g_A^q{}^2) (q + \bar{q})$$

$$F_3^{\gamma Z} = \sum_q 2e_q^2 g_A^q (q - \bar{q})$$

$$F_3^Z = \sum_q 2g_V^q g_A^q (q - \bar{q})$$

Neutral current

$$F_2^{W^-} = 2x(u + \bar{d} + \bar{s} + c \dots)$$

$$F_3^{W^-} = 2x(u - \bar{d} - \bar{s} + c \dots)$$

$$W^+ : u \rightarrow d \dots$$

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Charged current

Weak interaction and F_3

ZEUS

ZEUS

- Search for missing transverse momentum from neutrino
- Reconstruct DIS kinematics via hadronic final state (Jaquet-Blondel method)
- Expected lepton beam polarization dependent cross section seen
- Additional flavor sensitivity, eg e^+ beam \rightarrow $d+s$ and anti u and anti c

Polarized inclusive DIS

- Virtual photon γ^* can only couple to quarks of opposite helicity
- Select either $q^+(x)$ or $q^-(x)$ by changing the orientation of target nucleon spin or helicity of incident lepton beam
- Calculate Asymmetry A_1 between 1/2 and 3/2 cross sections:

$$A_1(x) \cong \frac{\sigma_{1/2} - \sigma_{3/2}}{\sigma_{1/2} + \sigma_{3/2}} = \frac{g_1(x)}{F_1(x)} \stackrel{LO}{=} \frac{\sum_q e_q^2 \Delta q(x)}{\sum_q e_q^2 q(x)}$$

- Similar to A_{LL} in p+p collisions
- inclusive DIS: only scattered e' info used, semi-inclusive: also detect final-state hadron and use FFs

polarized proton structure

$$\frac{d^2 \Delta\sigma^i}{dx dy} = \frac{2\pi\alpha^2}{xyQ^2} \eta^i \left[Y_+ 2g_5^i - g_L^i \mp Y_- 2xg_1^i + y^2 g_L^i \right]$$

$$g_L^i = g_4^i - 2xg_5^i$$

$$Y_{\pm} = 1 \pm (1-y)^2$$

- g_1 measures **charge square** weighted total quark spin contribution to the nucleon (not $\Delta\Sigma$!)
- Flavor information from γZ interference, Z exchange and in particular charged current (W exchange) interactions

$$g_1^\gamma = x \sum_q e_q^2 (\Delta q + \Delta \bar{q})$$

$$g_1^{\gamma Z} = x \sum_q 2e_q g_V^q (\Delta q + \Delta \bar{q})$$

$$g_1^Z = x \sum_q (g_V^q)^2 (\Delta q + \Delta \bar{q})$$

$$g_5^{\gamma Z} = \sum_q 2e_q^2 g_A^q (\Delta q - \Delta \bar{q})$$

$$g_5^Z = \sum_q 2g_V^q g_A^q (\Delta q - \Delta \bar{q})$$

6/21/2021

Neutral current

$$g_1^{W^-} = (\Delta u + \Delta \bar{d} + \Delta \bar{s} + \Delta c \dots)$$

$$g_5^{W^-} = (\Delta u - \Delta \bar{d} - \Delta \bar{s} + \Delta c \dots)$$

$$W^+ : u \rightarrow d \dots$$

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Charged current

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Real W production as access to (anti)quark helicities

- Maximally parity violating V-A interaction selects only **lefthanded** quarks and **righthanded** antiquarks:

→ Having different helicities for the incoming proton then selects spin parallel or antiparallel of the quarks

→ Difference of the cross sections gives quark helicities $\Delta q(x)$

- No Fragmentation function required

- Very high scale defined by W mass

p helicity +

p helicity -

Bourelly , Soffer
Nucl.Phys. B423 (1994) 329-348

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SIDIS Kinematics

Detect also final-state hadron(s) and make use of flavor sensitivity of Fragmentation functions

Current fragmentation: related to struck quark

Target fragmentation: related to nucleon remnant

$$P_h^- = z k^-$$

Fractional hadron momentum wrt to parton momentum ($0 < z < 1$)

$$\frac{d^3\sigma}{dx dQ^2 dz} \stackrel{LO}{\propto} \sum_{q, \bar{q}} e_q^2 q(x, Q^2) D_{1,q}^h(z, Q^2)$$

Quark distribution functions: (anti)quark q in nucleon with momentum fraction x

Fragmentation functions: quark $q \rightarrow$ hadron h

Formal definition of PDFs and FFs in SIDIS

Handbag diagram (*Im* part of forward scattering amplitude)

- **Factorization** of non-perturbative (PDF, FF) and perturbative parts of cross section
- PDFs and FFs **universal**
- Each blob can be described in quark-parton model by bi-local quark/parton fields and hadronic final state X (= everything else)

Definitions II

$$\Xi_{ij} = \sum_X \int \frac{d^3 P_X}{16\pi^3 E_X} \int d^4 \xi \exp^{ip \cdot \xi} \langle 0 | \psi_i(\xi) | P_h S_h, X \rangle \langle P_h S_h, X | \bar{\psi}_j(0) | 0 \rangle$$

$$\Phi_{ij} = \int d^4 \xi \exp^{ik \cdot \xi} \langle PS | \bar{\psi}_j(0) \psi_i(\xi) | PS \rangle$$

- Distribution and fragmentation functions as traces over Dirac matrix combinations:

- Vector (momentum structure: $f_1(x)$, $D_1(z)$)
- Axial Vector (helicity structure: $g_1(x)$, $G_1(z)$)
- Tensor (helicity flip structure: $h_1(x)$, $H_1(z)$)

In light-cone coordinates dominating momenta are related to in(out) going hadron long.

momenta:

$$k^\mu \approx x P^\mu + \mathbf{k}_T^\mu$$

$$p^\mu \approx 1/z P_h^\mu + \mathbf{p}_T^\mu$$

[Barone, Drago, Ratcliffe: Phys.Rept. 359 \(2002\)](#)

Factorization and Universality

- Physics processes can be factorized into small distance and large distance behaviour:
 - Small distance: asymptotic freedom \rightarrow perturbative QCD calculation
 - Large distance: confinement, need to be measured!

- Non-perturbative functions universal (same in ep, p+p or e^+e^-)

$$d\sigma_{ep} \approx f_1^a(x_a) \frac{d\hat{\sigma}_{ab \rightarrow cd}}{d\hat{t}} D_1(z_c, M_c^2)$$

$$d\sigma_{pp} \approx f_1^a(x_a) f_1^b(x_b) \frac{d\hat{\sigma}_{ab \rightarrow cd}}{d\hat{t}} D_1(z_c, M_c^2)$$

What can fragmentation functions do?

- Flavor sensitivity:

at high z : $D_{1,u}^{\pi^+} \gg D_{1,u}^{\pi^-}$; $s \rightarrow K$, $c \rightarrow D$, etc

- Spin sensitivity (via transfer):

Polarized FFs G_1 and H_1 from long/transv. spin of parton

- Transverse momentum sensitivity

Access to 3D momentum structure (but convolutions)

- Transverse spin sensitivity via unpolarized hadron(s)

Azimuthal distribution of hadrons (Collins FF, Interference)

- Mass/spin dependence of particle production:

$$D_u^{\pi} > D_u^K \stackrel{?}{>} D_u^{\rho}$$

Back to the Spin: Helicities

DSSV

- Precise SIDIS measurements from HERMES, COMPASS, SMC at $0.01 > x > 0.3$

- Global fits of polarized DIS and SIDIS data constrain valence quarks well
- sea quark sensitivity still limited (and assumption dependent)

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- Little sensitivity to gluons for (SI)DIS

So, how does that tie in with RHIC-Spin? **Gluons**

- Only limited gluon access via DIS data through DGLAP evolution (no large Q^2 lever arm for polarized PDFs until the EIC)
- Some access in SIDIS through high P_t hadrons and charmed mesons (low statistics, will again require the higher energies of the EIC)

Unpolarized gluon PDFs
are ok thanks to HERA

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g_1 data only from fixed target DIS, **so far!**

Gluon polarization

- Barely access via DIS data through DGLAP evolution (no large Q^2 lever arm)
 - Some access in SIDIS through high Pt hadrons and charmed mesons
 - Polarized pp collisions at LO in α_s sensitive to gluons
- long. double spin asymmetries A_{LL} access Δg

Reaction	Dom. partonic process	probes	LO Feynman diagram
$\bar{p}\bar{p} \rightarrow \pi + X$	$\bar{g}\bar{g} \rightarrow gg$ $\bar{q}\bar{q} \rightarrow qg$	Δg	
$\bar{p}\bar{p} \rightarrow \text{jet}(s) + X$	$\bar{g}\bar{g} \rightarrow gg$ $\bar{q}\bar{q} \rightarrow qg$	Δg	(as above)
$\bar{p}\bar{p} \rightarrow \gamma + X$ $\bar{p}\bar{p} \rightarrow \gamma + \text{jet} + X$	$\bar{q}\bar{q} \rightarrow \gamma q$ $\bar{q}\bar{q} \rightarrow \gamma q$	Δg Δg	
$\bar{p}\bar{p} \rightarrow \gamma\gamma + X$	$\bar{q}\bar{q} \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$	$\Delta q, \Delta \bar{q}$	
$\bar{p}\bar{p} \rightarrow DX, BX$	$\bar{g}\bar{g} \rightarrow c\bar{c}, b\bar{b}$	Δg	

More about gluon spin: Rapidities, etc

- In p+p always convolutions of x_1 and $x_2 \rightarrow$ only indirect knowledge about x dependence
- Try to tune it differently:
 - Higher/lower energy
 - Different rapidity ranges (asymmetric x_1 x_2)
 - Di-jets($m=x_1x_2s$, + rapidity)

Sea quark helicities from W production

- W production provides flavor sensitivity:
- W⁺ production u + dbar
- W⁻ production d + ubar

What about transverse spin?

S.Pisano, Transversity 14

		Quark polarization		
		Unpolarized (U)	Longitudinally Polarized (L)	Transversely Polarized (T)
Nucleon Polarization	U	$f_1 = \odot$		$h_1^\perp = \odot \downarrow - \odot \uparrow$
	L		$g_1 = \odot \rightarrow - \odot \leftarrow$ helicities	$h_{1L}^\perp = \odot \nearrow - \odot \nwarrow$
	T	$f_{1T}^\perp = \odot \uparrow - \odot \downarrow$	$g_{1T} = \odot \rightarrow - \odot \leftarrow$	$h_1 = \odot \uparrow - \odot \downarrow$ transversity $h_{1T}^\perp = \odot \nearrow - \odot \nwarrow$

- Only f_1 , g_1 and h_1 survive integration over transverse momentum
- Rest: Explicitly transverse momentum dependent (x, k_T) - TMD, similar for FFs

Transversity properties

- Helicity flip amplitude
- Chiral odd
- Since all interactions conserve chirality one needs another chiral odd object \rightarrow Fragmentation function or other chiral-odd PDF (DY)
- Does not couple to gluons \Rightarrow different QCD evolution than $\Delta q(x)$
- Valence dominated \Rightarrow Comparable to Lattice calculations, especially tensor charge:

$$g_T = \int_0^1 dx [\delta q(x) - \delta \bar{q}(x)]$$

$$q(x) = q_+(x) + q_-(x) \sim \text{Im}(\mathcal{A}_{++,++} + \mathcal{A}_{+-,+-})$$

$$\Delta q(x) = q_+(x) - q_-(x) \sim \text{Im}(\mathcal{A}_{++,++} - \mathcal{A}_{+-,+-})$$

$$\delta q(x) = q_{\uparrow}(x) - q_{\downarrow}(x) \sim \text{Im}\mathcal{A}_{+,-,-+}$$

Positivity bound:

$$|\delta q(x)| \leq q(x)$$

Soffer bound:

$$|\delta q(x)| \leq \frac{1}{2} (q(x) + \Delta q(x))$$

Sivers Function

$$f_{1T}^\perp(x, k_T)$$

- Proton–spin – quark orbit (k_T) correlation
- Suggested in '93 – “zero” due to time reversal
- Brodsky-Hwang-Schmid '02 model example of Sivers function using gauge links
- Belitsky-Yuan '02 → gauge links generally needed
- Collins → function can exist, but modified universality (**the SIGN change**)

(Transversity x) Collins Function

$$h_1(x, k_T) H_1^\perp(z, p_T)$$

- **Quark spin** – hadron transverse momentum correlation (in fragmentation)
- Analyzer for quark transversity → access to tensor charge (Lattice, BSM?)
- A polarized (ie signed) fragmentation function
- Transverse momentum conservation requires some compensation (Terayev-Schaefer)

Figs from Buffing et al. :
[PRD 86 \(2012\) 074030](https://arxiv.org/abs/1207.4030)
 R.Seidl, Spm

Collins fragmentation function

J. Collins, Nucl. Phys. B396, (1993) 161

$$D_{q\uparrow}^h(z, P_{h\perp}) = D_{1,q}^h(z, P_{h\perp}^2) + H_{1,q}^{\perp h}(z, P_{h\perp}^2) \frac{(\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{P}_{h\perp}) \cdot \mathbf{S}_q}{zM_h}$$

- Spin of quark correlates with hadron transverse momentum

→ translates into azimuthal anisotropy of final state hadrons

- Chiral-odd, required for access to transversity

Sivers/Collins/etc measurements in SIDIS

- $ep^{\uparrow} \rightarrow e'hX$
- A_{UT} asymmetries
(Unpolarized lepton beam,
Transversely polarized target)
- Different azimuthal modulations related to Sivers effect ($\sin(\phi - \phi_s)$) and Collins effect ($\sin(\phi + \phi_s)$)
- Other modulations related to Boer-Mulders and other functions

Status for TMDs

- Sivers and Collins measurements are solidly established by HERMES, COMPASS (+Belle)
- Global fits of SIDIS data exist, **but still very limited**
- p+p inclusion not quite as straightforward except:
 - hadron in jet Collins measurements (requires Jet function, some results from STAR)
 - Di-hadron fragmentation function measurements (transversity, some STAR results)
- Drell-Yan important as test of Sivers sign change (some COMPASS and STAR Z/W data)

Transverse single spin asymmetries

- Large left-right asymmetries A_N seen in polarized pp collisions from low energies up to highest RHIC energies
- Both **initial state** and **final state** effects contribute in the same asymmetries
- TMD interpretation not directly applicable as only one scale process instead of 2 scales (P_T in p+p vs Q^2 and P_{hT})
- Higher twist interpretation is applicable

Phys.Rev. D90 (2014) 7, 072008

Phys.Rev. D90 (2014) 1, 012006

p+p A_N s

- Higher Twist origins are correlation functions (quark-gluon-quark, tri-gluon handbags)
- These correlations exist for initial state (proton side) and final state (fragmentation)
- Many TMDs are related to the correlators via moments over intrinsic transverse momenta, such as Efremov-Teraev-Qiu-Sterman function T_F and Siverson function
- First global fit of SIDIS, e+e-, and p+p A_N s (large transverse spin contribution [PRD 102 \(2020\) 054002](https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.04002))

g-g correlation (trigluon)

q-g correlation

Difficulties in A_N interpretations

- “higher twist should be $1/P_T$ suppressed”
- Asymmetries for “isolated π^0 are larger than with other photons nearby”
- A dependence of A_N s puzzling: larger suppression at lower x_F , smaller suppression at higher x_F ; not really in CGC range
- Accord to theory calculations happens at even higher PT
- Possibility of other sources (diffractive) or just fragmentation effect (larger correlation to parton at high z)
- other nuclear effects at play

Exclusive (spin) physics

- Exclusive: Full final state gets detected, proton (or a nucleon) stays intact
- DVCS: $ep \rightarrow e'p'\gamma$
- excl. VM/PS production
- Physics: Generalized Parton Distributions ($E, H, \tilde{E}, \tilde{H}, E_T \dots$)
 - related to Ji sum rule
→ orbital angular momentum
 - parton imaging in b_T in position space

$$J_q = \frac{1}{2} \Delta \Sigma_q + L_q = \lim_{t, \xi \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2} \int dx x [H^q(x, \xi, t) + E^q(x, \xi, t)] .$$

Spatial imaging of gluon density

➤ Exclusive vector meson production:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dx_B dQ^2 dt}$$

- ✧ Fourier transform of the t-dep
- ➡ Spatial imaging of glue density
- ✧ Resolution $\sim 1/Q$ or $1/M_Q$

➤ Gluon imaging from simulation:

$$W^2 = (p + q)^2; \quad M_N^2 = p^2$$

Images of gluons
from exclusive
J/ψ production

What comes next?

→ EIC

- 80% polarized electrons from 5-18 GeV
- 70% polarized protons from 40-275 GeV
- Ions from 40-110 GeV/u
- Polarized light ions 40 -184 GeV (He^3)
- 1000x HERA luminosities: 10^{33} - $10^{34} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$
- CMS energies $\sqrt{s} = 29 - 140 \text{ GeV}$

QCD at high gluon densities

- Saturation effects

Nuclear effects

- Nuclear PDFs
- Passage of color through nuclear matter (nFFs, pT broadening)

Spin of the nucleon:

- Gluon spin
- Role Sea quarks

Tomography :

- 3D momentum structure (q, g Sivers, Tensor charge, TMD Evolution)
- 3D spatial structure

Origin of the Mass

- Axial anomaly contributions
- Hadron structure

Other

- Spectroscopy (XYZ)
- EW physics
- Other

EIC impact for Sivers Functions

- Precise nucleon image in momentum space of quarks, sea-quarks and gluons

Vladimirov, et al

Xiao, et al

Tensor charges

Single hadron channel (Pitonyak)

Di-hadron channel (Radici)

Radici: Spin

- Precise determination of tensor charges via Collins and di-hadron channels
- Better precision than lattice \rightarrow potential access to BSM physics in case of discrepancies
- Full integrals, role of sea quark transversity

Gluon and sea polarization

- 1 year of EIC running will pin down gluon polarization
- Using SIDIS precise determination of sea quark helicities, especially strange contribution of interest
- Indirect determination of orbital angular momentum via sum rule
- Also interesting access to flavor via charged current reactions

[hep-ph:2007.08300](https://arxiv.org/abs/hep-ph/2007.08300)

Impact of inclusive DIS + PVDIS on Quark and gluon spin

- Detailed studies also for inclusive channels, inclusive CC A_1 s
- Impact on g_1 structure function and spin sum rule for different scenarios

Sato et. al.

Unpolarized PDFs

- Impact on unpolarized PDFs from plain (NC) DIS, PV (CC) DIS and SIDIS
- Also potential access to intrinsic charm

Pion/Kaon structure

- Use Sullivan process to extract pion/Kaon Form Factors and PDFs

Saturation physics

- Updates on the feasibility of back-to-back di-jet measurements
- Possibility of coherent J/Psi measurements

nPDFs

- Detailed impact studies on nPDF measurements, including comparisons for different global fitters
- Other topics related to HI physics

FFs

- Fragmentation functions provide information on struck parton, its flavor and spin
- They are a staple of all SIDIS measurements
- Also their understanding will improve further with the EIC

nFFs

- Expected impact from EIC on light hadron nuclear FFs
- Also more sophisticated studies ongoing (transverse momentum broadening, nu dependence, etc)
- Similar studies for heavy flavor

Spectroscopy: XYZs

- Proper Generators for exotics at EIC prepared
- Requirement for forward electron (or muon) ID

Beam energies: 5_41

Beam energies: 5_100

Beam energies: 10_100

Beam energies: 18_275

Kinematics at an EIC

- Need full coverage over a large range of rapidities
- Scattered leptons to backward/central rapidities
- Hadronic final state in the forward/central region
- Auxilliary detectors far forward (ZDCs, roman pots)
- Auxilliary detectors far backward (low Q^2 tagger)
- Dedicated polarimetry/luminosity detectors

Summary

- The study of the spin structure of the nucleons allows us to better understand the most fundamental properties of them and of QCD
- Various processes $e+p$ (DIS), $p+p$ collisions and $e+e^-$ annihilation provide different access to distribution and fragmentation functions
- Universality and Factorization ensure that we are dealing with the same functions
- Helicity structure:
 - Related to the main spin sum rule
 - (sea)Quark helicities via SIDIS and W production in $p+p$
 - Gluons via $p+p$ (and eventually scaling violation of DIS)
- Transverse structure:
 - TMD functions like Sivers/Collins effects in two-scale processes (SIDIS, hadron-in-jet, etc)
 - $p+p$ Ans probe higher twist functions (but related via moments)
- Exclusive processes (DVCS, etc) to access GPDs and Orbital angular momentum
- Some interesting possibilities still at RHIC, then EIC